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APPLICATION OF GEOINFORMATICS FOR IDENTIFICATION AND DETECTION OF URBAN SPRAWL IN AND AROUND PUNE REGION

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Abstract

Due to the modern breakthrough technological developments and rapid pace of urbanization as well as the haphazard growth of major cities has ushered- in, into one of the surmounting challenges which is menacingly faced by almost all the countries of the world. More so, this situation has worsened in India in a more pronounced fashion. As unorganized urbanization is becoming the major problem and primarily order of the day, it requires the immediate attention of technocrats/administrators for sustainable development of urban regions. In the emerging scenario it is essential to have updated information on urban growth patterns and its influence on the obtaining environments.

In recent years, the data analysis has indicated land cover as well as land use has undergone tremendous changes due to escalating and indiscriminate anthropogenic constructional developments. This paper will also examine the effective use of GIS and RS of near-real-time change detection of the Land Use Land Cover (LULC) and urban sprawl of the study area.

An attempt has been made to develop a change detection of Urban Sprawl in Pune Municipality Corporation (PMC) of Maharashtra state, over a time period of 14 years (1992 – 2006). Visual interpretation technique has been used to classify the satellite imageries .The study has been conducted using LANDSAT ETM+ of the year 1992, 1999 and 2006. A

new map has been developed showing the features of increase and decrease of the study area. Thus, it is further hoped that this paper will evince keen interest among the erudite readers/researchers, and will be of immense help to the municipal corporation authorities.

Keywords: LULC, ERDAS, LANDSAT, SPRAWL

INTRODUCTION

Human is the most progressive creature on the earth. For his progress he has made many changes on this earth such as Industrialization, Urbanization, architecture etc. which has since taken place. In this competitive world man has migrated himself from rural area to urban regions. Due to this there is huge increase day by day in population in the urban cities vis-à-vis there is a tremendous demand for dwelling places and hence there is enormous enhancement in the growth rate of these cities. This has raised the indiscriminate urban expansion problem all over the world.

Growing cities are creating an alarming situation all over the world. Due to the rapid process of urbanization, & the haphazard growth of these major cities, one of the challenging task in front of any country is to curb the township growth. Many developing countries are facing the critical problems like population growth, poverty and income distribution, unemployment, urbanization and internal migration, agriculture, rural development, and quality education. Thus, among these problems of urbanization is the major problem and it requires the immediate attention for sustainable development of the urban land as well as town planning. Urbanization, which may be broadly defined as the process of expanding urban influence, has been taking place for more than 6000 years, has increased markedly since the beginning of this century.

One distinctive feature of India's urbanization is increasing metropolitan migration. India's big cities now account for a large share of total urban population. In 2002, the share of metropolitan cities was 37.8 % up from 32.5% in 1992. The trend indicates continued urbanization in the years to come. It clearly implies that with rapid growth of million plus cities, the problem of land management will be more and more complex with the passage of the time. The forces and processes of technological development, globalization and population growth accelerate the dynamics of urbanization process in the developing countries. This "accelerated" phase of urban transition from rural in developing countries, population from migration and endogenous growth of those large prime cities and industrial location on their fringes are actually expanding the urban areas. This is mainly due to the rapid growth in the IT sector. Although, IT industry in India has more than three decades of history, its take-off into major software industries is a recent phenomenon. Not all cities in India were able to respond quickly to the demands of these new service industries. This is evident from the fact that the larger Metros of India (Mumbai, Delhi, Chennai and Kolkata) have not been as successful as the second rung of cities like Hyderabad, Bangalore and Pune.

Pune, the eighth highly populated metropolitan city of India is undergoing a rapid metamorphosis, which will be of our interest and part of this study. At this juncture, the state of the art technologies like Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information System (GIS) can play an important role. Remote Sensing is broadly defined as science of acquiring information about a physical phenomenon of an object on the surface of the earth measured at a distance without being in physical contact with the object of interest. GIS is defined as a combination of Hardware, Software, data, users used to manage, analyze and understand spatially related data to solve management and planning issues.

Also Pune is second Largest city of Maharashtra state. At present population of Pune city is around 31,57,000 as per 2001 census Population of Pune has increased by 56 % over the last decade which reflects tremendous increase making it more congested than ever. The expansion process is still continuing both due to its own population expansion and the influx from surrounding areas. Understanding the growth and changes brought on by urbanization is critical to those who must manage resources and provide services in these rapidly changing environments.

The rapid population growth has caused heavy pressure on city administration regarding issues of transportation, atmospheric pollution, water supply, sewage, electric power and other civic amenities with impacts on population at large. Since, the provision of most civic services to the public involves geographic aspects there is a logical need that all the agencies responsible for providing basic urban facilities to the citizens should have accurate maps, rectified to a common geographic reference for use in the urban environment. Unfortunately, hand-made sketches of civic infrastructure without any grid reference are being developed and used by each agency for the achievement of their respective goals. Moreover, maps are seldom updated after any specified time-interval. Resultantly, there is non-conformity in the precincts of various administrative divides depictive of Town, Union Council, and Population census units.

Therefore in the present study our endeavor has been to update and make all the maps appropriate (near-real-time data) as ready reckoner for the esteemed customers'/users' benefit with the help of latest techniques like GIS & RS.

Town Planning Development and Sprawl

A proper town development and growth of town should take place on some principles as under:

- * Green buildings and Housing and proper regional planning
- * Public & Residential buildings
- * Institutional areas- and its expansion.
- * Transportation and road system
- * Recreational areas and Shopping Malls
- * Secretariat, courts and other central places like Railway stations, Bus stops etc.
- * Play fields, Gardens, Water bodies for entertainments etc.

Sprawl generally refers to some type of development with change trends of landuse and an impact such as loss of agriculture land, open space, and ecologically sensitive habitats. Also sometimes sprawl is equated with growth of town or city (radial spread). In simpler words, as population increases in an area or a city, the boundary of the city expands to accommodate the growth; this expansion is considered as Sprawl.

Usually sprawls take place on the urban fringe, at the edge of an urban area or along the highways. Sprawl is considered to be an unplanned outgrowth of urban centres along the periphery of the cities, along highways, along the road connecting a city, etc. Due to lack of prior planning these outgrowths are devoid of basic amenities like water, electricity, sanitation, etc. Provision of certain infrastructure facilities like new roads and highways, fuel such sprawls that ultimately result in inefficient and drastic change in land use affecting the ecosystem and has negative on impact on environments and health.

What is 'Urban Sprawl'/ Rural & Suburban Sprawl?

The term urban sprawl coined by William Whyte (1958) has developed through much deliberation and now can be given a reasonably precise definition: "Urban sprawl is the growth of a metropolitan area through the process of scattered development of miscellaneous types of land use in isolated locations on the fringe, followed by the gradual filling-in of the intervening spaces with similar uses". Urban sprawl, and the economic and regulatory systems which create it, not only produce an inefficient and unpleasant environment on the urban fringe, but adversely affect the inner city and the rural areas as well. (Bosselman, 1968). Generally the change trend is referred as urban & rural sprawl.

Urban Sprawl- Forms, Patterns, Types:

Forms of Sprawl

Sprawl developments consist of three basic spatial forms -

Low- Density Sprawl-

Low density sprawl is the consumptive use of land for urban purposes along the margin of existing metropolitan areas. This type of sprawl is supported by piecemeal extension of basic urban infrastructure such as water, sewage, power and roads.

Ribbon Pattern

Ribbon sprawl is development that follows major transportation corridors outward from urban cores. Land adjacent to corridors are developed but those without direct access remain in rural uses/covers. Over times these nearby 'raw' lands may be converted to urban uses as land value increase and infrastructure is extended perpendicularly from the major roads and lines.

Leapfrog Development-

Leapfrog development is a discontinuous pattern of urbanization, with patches of developed lands that are widely separated from each other and from the boundaries, albeit blurred in cases of recognized, urbanized areas. This form of development is the most costly with respect to providing the urban services, such as water and sewage.

Need for Studying Urban, Rural and Suburban Sprawl

In industrialised countries the future growth of urban and suburban populations will be comparatively modest since their population growth rates are low and over 80% of their population already live in urban areas. Conversely, developing countries are in the middle of the transition process, when growth rates are highest. The exceptional growth of many urban agglomerations in many developing countries is the result of a threefold structural change process: the transition away from agricultural employment, high overall population growth, and increasing urbanisation rates (Grubler, 1994). The biggest challenge for science, engineering and technology in the 21st century is how to ensure adequate housing, sanitation and health, and transportation services in a habitable urban environment in developing countries. Sprawl is seen as one of the potential threats for such development.

Identification of the causes of urban sprawl

Conditions favorable to urban sprawl can be identified as follows:

1. Lower land price compared to developed areas of the main city
2. Availability of un-built agricultural land
3. High rate of urbanization and rapid development activities
4. Availability of some municipal services in mixed development without paying for it
5. Less control on urban development being located outside the urban limit
6. Lower taxes on industries
7. Influence of speculators on the agricultural land owners for selling land to developers
8. High rate of urbanization
9. Results of failure to match demand of urban infrastructure and services

Role of GIS and Remote Sensing in identifying change detection of Urban Sprawl

In general, the mapping of urban areas by Remote Sensing is a rather complex process due to the heterogeneity of the urban environment, typically consisting of built-up structures (Buildings, transportation nets), several kinds of vegetation cover (Parks, gardens, agricultural areas), barren lands and water bodies (Barnsley et al., 1993).

The monitoring of urban development is mainly to find out the type, the amount and location of land conversion for future planning. Although various studies have been dedicated to measure and monitor the growth and sprawl of urban form they have limitations in capturing the characteristics of urban sprawl. Here is a technique - the change detection- specially to measure the sprawl is developed within the integration of remote sensing and GIS. The advantages of the change detection method are its simplicity and easy integration with GIS.

Remote sensing and GIS can be used separately or in combination for application in studies of urban sprawl. In the case of a combined application, an efficient, even though more complex approach is the integration of remote sensing data processing, GIS analyses, database manipulation and models into a single analyses system. Such an integrated analysis, monitoring and forecasting system based on GIS and database management system technologies requires an understanding of the problem and the application of available technologies.

The physical expressions and patterns of sprawl on landscapes can be detected, mapped, and analyzed using remote sensing and geographical information system (GIS) with image processing and classification. The patterns of sprawl are being described using a variety of metrics and through visual interpretation techniques. In Land Use Planning for Urban Sprawl bring out the techniques for mapping suburban sprawl. They evaluate the traditional unsupervised classification and proposed GIS buffering approach for mapping the suburban sprawl. The problems associated with the classification of urban classes (built-up) in comparison with rural and urban centers can also be addresses using RS and GIS.

Study Area

Present Pune Municipal Corporation Limit has been selected as the study area. Pune, formerly known as Poona, is the second largest city in the state of Maharashtra in western India, around 160 kilometers southeast of the state capital, Mumbai. It is also the seventh largest city in India. The city of Pune, located in the State of Maharashtra and lies between the North Latitude 18o 30' and 18o 40' and between East Longitude. The study area is included in Survey of India topographic sheet nos. 47 F/10, 11, 14 and 15 on 1:50,000 scale. As per 2001 census of India, the population of Pune urban agglomeration is 3,529,900. Growth in the software and education sectors has led to an influx of skilled labor from across India. The migrating population rose from 43,900 in 2001 to 88,200 in 2005. Almost 40 percent of Pune's population lives in slums. The sharp increase in censorial decade of 1991-2001 can be attributed to absorption of 38 fringe villages into Pune Metropolitan.

Methodology Adopted for the Present Study

The digital remote sensing data was processed and geo referenced in Erdas 9.2 software. Initially the shape -file of Pune Municipal Corporation has been collected, then make out a subset from the LANDSAT image. The enhanced image classified into different classes by using Erdas imagines and compared with land use maps. The classification is unsupervised in nature. The image has been classified into following classes- Urban, Wasteland, Vegetation, River and Agriculture. The geo-referenced images were studied for the land use and land cover change analysis in the Arc view environment. The flowchart of the methodology has been given as under at Fig.1

Fig1. Flowchart of Methodology

Synthesis and Discussion of Results

- 1. The following subset was obtained after using ERDAS IMAGINE 9.1**

Fig2. 1992 IMAGE FOR PUNE

1999 IMAGE FOR PUNE

2006 IMAGE FOR PUNE

Unsupervised Classification using Maximum Like-hood rule and the following Classes were generated with color code

Classification Classes	Color code
Water Bodies	Blue
Urban	Red
Vegetation	Green
Agriculture	Yellow
Wasteland	Brown

Fig5. Interpretation Key

CLASSIFIED IMAGE

Fig6. Classified image for 1992

Fig7. Classified image for 1999

Fig8. Classified image for 2006

2. CHANGE DETECTION

Fig9.Change Detection image for1992- 1999 Fig10.Change-Detection image for 1999-2006

Analysis for the Urban Sprawl Study

CLASSES	Year 1992	Year 1999
WATER BODIES	361.451	291.192
URBAN	2186.09	4710.56
VEGETATION	11350.1	9149.44
AGRICULTURE	5870.46	3030.67
WASTELAND	5459.21	8145.41

Table 1.Comparative study of change detection (in hectare) from the year 1992-1999:

Fig11. Comparative study of change detection (in hectare) from the year 1992-1999

CLASSES	% change from 1992 to 1999
WATER BODIES	24.1% decrease of the total area
URBAN	53.6% increase of the total area
VEGETATION	24.3% decrease of the total area
AGRICULTURE	93.7% decrease of the total area
WASTELAND	32.1% increase of the total area

Table2. Change detection of land-use in percentage (%) from the year 1992- 1999

The satellite imagery soft data has been procured from National Remote Sensing Centre, Hyderabad for preparation of Land use / Land cover layer. The land use changes rather land cover changes were studied LANDSAT image. Land use / Land cover layer represents the digital image of the city classified in five land use classes, namely: urban area, wasteland, agricultural land, vegetation and water bodies. The areas under change was measured and presented in a tabular form to get the clear picture of land use and land cover change. In broad terms, between 1992 and 1999, the major change was detected in the barren land use, built up area category. Except for these three, all other uses showed a decline. In the 1999 land use map of Pune, agricultural land use was decrease by 93% of the total area of the city from 1992. The increase in agricultural land use in the year 1999 was, mainly due to some area, which was not covered in 1992 shown as agricultural use in 1999. From 1992 to 1999 barren land or wasteland was increased by 32%. From 1992 to 1999 water bodies was decreased by 24%. From the year 1992 to 1999 the agricultural land is decreased by 93% of the total area of that span. The study mainly concentrated on the built-up area, since that was considered as prime indicator of urban development. The built-up and vegetation area of 1992 from LANDSAT image was classified in ERDAS imagine environment and was compared with the satellite image of 1999. The total built-up area of PMC from 1992 to 1999 was increased by 53% of the total area of that span.

CLASSES	Year 1999	Year 2006
WATER BODIES	291.192	289.53
URBAN	4710.09	5438.34
VEGETATION	9048.535	11047.59
AGRICULTURE	3030.67	3339.09
WASTELAND	8145.41	5123.43

Table 3. Comparative study of change detection (in hectare) from the year 1999-2006

Fig12. Comparative study of change detection (in hectare) from the year 1999-2006

Change detection of land-use in percentage (%) from the year 1999 to 2006:

CLASSES	% change from 1999 to 2006
WATER BODIES	0.6% decrease of the total area
URBAN	13.9% increase of the total area
VEGETATION	18.1% increase of the total area
AGRICULTURE	9.24% increase of the total area
WASTELAND	58.1% decrease of the total area

Table 4. Change detection of land-use in percentage (%) from the year 1999- 2006

Land Use Change From 1999-2006

The land use changes were studied from Landsat image. The major change was detected in the barren land use category and significant change in agricultural and commercial. From the year of 1999 to 2006 land use map of Pune, agricultural land use increased by 9.23% of the total area of the city. The increase in agricultural land use in the year 2006 would be really beneficial for farmers. With this vegetation land use there is bit change in barren and fallow land also found. From the year 1999 to 2006 the wasteland was decreased by 58.98%. From the year 1999 to 2006 the built up area or urban land was increased by

13.4% . From the year 1999 to 2006 the fallow land and vegetation was increased by 9.23% and 18% respectively. The analysis revealed that almost 70-80% of open/vacant/cultivable land was brought under urban land use. Most of the vacant lands close to the roads are converted for residential purpose or are under construction. In between some vacant lands are occupied with brick kilns, marble stockyards and stone quarries. The open lands located inside the city, were mostly converted into big shopping complexes/malls or hotels. The open areas, close to the outskirts of the city, are mostly turned into big townships, new colonies, Institutions and apartment complexes. The land use indirectly reflects the land values, as the prices in the fringe areas are much lower than the areas near the central areas of the city. Presently the land values are increasing along the urban fringe areas due to great demand.

Results Pertaining to Urban Sprawl

CLASS	1992	1999	2006
URBAN	2186.09 Hectares	4710.56 Hectares	5438.34 Hectares

Table5. Distribution of Land Cover for Urban Built-Up

Fig13. Distribution of Land Cover for Urban Built-Up

CLASS	WATER BODIES	URBAN	VEGETATION	AGRICULTURE	WASTELAND
URBAN	2.62	859.78	647.51	92.69	583.68

Table6. Change detection of built-up area/urban area (in hectare) from the year 1992 to 1999:

Fig 14. Change detection of the built-up area/urban area (in hectare) from the year 1992 to 1999

CLASS	WATER BODIES	URBAN	VEGETATION	AGRICULTURE	WASTELAND
URBAN	4.7	2323.7	1249.241	256.25	876.1

Table7. Change detection of built-up area/urban area (in hectare) from the year 1999 to 2006

Fig 15. Change detection of the built –up area/urban area (in hectare) from the year 1999 to 2006

Areas of the Urban Sprawl

An analysis of satellite imagery of the city has indicated that Pune is experiencing "haphazard growth" with a high intensity of urban sprawl, leading to increasing pressure on urban infrastructure. Continuing growth on the existing pattern could lead to unsustainable development unless proper management systems are introduced on priority, and for this we used remote sensing data and geographical information systems (GIS) for the project.

Fig 16 Area of urban sprawl in 2006

In this particular study change detection has been used to identify the amount of Urban Sprawl in the year between 1999 to 2006. It is that the growth in Pune's periphery is happening in a haphazard manner and even hill slopes are beginning to be occupied. This project covered the area which merged under the Pune municipal corporation (PMC), Balewadi, Baner, Bavdhan-Khurda, Kalas, Dhanori, Mohammedwadi, Undri and Katraj are showing a high degree of sprawl. At the ward level, Aundh, Sangamwadi and Yerwada showing a high sprawl. The city is showing the highest degree of sprawl along the National Highways that pass through or skirt the city: the Pune-Bangalore NH-4, Katraj bypass, Pune-Ahmednagar and Pune-Solapur (NH-9) highways. While physical barriers such as hills and rivers are resulting in a "leapfrog pattern" of urban development around Pune, urban growth along the highways is leading to the "ribbon sprawl" pattern of development. Higher the intensity of urban sprawl, greater would be the pressure on the PMC's resources to provide roads, water and transport.

Reflections of the study

The planning and management of urban environment require huge amount of information regarding almost all Aspects of natural and man-made features of that area. Until lately, such a study could be achieved through days of exhaustive Surveys, map generation and tedious calculations. GIS serve as a powerful tool for spatial and non-spatial analysis of data. In this study, an attempt has been made to apply the role of GIS in the management of urban environment. Urban environment basically consists of built up area, i.e. buildings, roads, industries, but in this study try to attend to some urban sprawl inside Pune urban activity zone. With using GIS techniques in the research we can understand how the modern technology can be used in the study of urban sprawl and its growth trend, updating and monitoring, Using repetitive coverage, urban environment especially land use/land cover and urban environment study on Pune Municipality

Conclusion

In the present paper, sprawling phenomenon has been studied with reference to its origin, haphazard development. Rural and Urban sprawl generally refers to haphazard growth which hampers and creates adverse impacts upon the ecological/ environmental natural setting. The present paper deals with the study of Pune, city which is 2nd largest metropolitan in the state of Maharashtra.

The present study demonstrated the efficiency of Remote Sensing and Geographic Information System as a tool in the study of land use /land covers changes due to urban sprawl. Particularly in the absence of required data from the local authorities, it gives fairly a good understanding of land use/land cover changes for a period of two decades, which in turn will be very helpful for local administrative bodies, decision makers, regional planners and stakeholders. Thus, this technology has the capability to provide the necessary input and intelligence for preparation of base maps, formulation of Planning proposals and act as a monitoring tool during the implementation phase. In this study, change detection has been used to identify the amount of urban sprawl in between the year of 1992 to 2006.

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